

The following artifacts are provided to support reproducibility of our research; the codebooks and interview guide can be found in the appendix of our paper.

1. **Interview Recruitment Messages:** Text used to recruit participants for the interview study, including messages sent to personal contacts, junior researchers, and researchers via cold email.
2. **Consent Form:** The version in use at the time of the study, prepared in accordance with the University's data protection policy. Key details are included here for reference.
3. **Demographics Questionnaire:** Questions about participants' background, including their experience in security and privacy (S&P) research, as well as their roles as authors, reviewers, and members of ethics boards.
4. **Interview Script:** The interview script was used to guide researchers during the study. As this was a semi-structured interview, we did not follow the script verbatim in every interview.